

**Investigation of Current Methods for Product Recommendation System in
E-Commerce Website**

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Computer System Engineering

Research on “Investigation of current methods for product recommendation system in E-Commerce Website” was carried out to gain new knowledge related to various approaches used for developing an E-Commerce product recommendation system. This research on computer system engineering degree would help to get an idea for developing a product recommendation algorithm.

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Abstract

Product Recommendation System becomes an essential factor in E-Commerce Website. Information overloading on the internet becomes a hazard for a customer to find the product based on their preferences. This research paper investigates and analyzes the current methods used for the recommendation of products. The investigated methods were mainly based on the content-filtering method, collaborative-filtering method, and hybrid-filtering method. All investigated methods were proposed and implemented to raise the standard of product recommendations for an E-Commerce Website. This paper also compared the various methods for the recommendation of products. This paper also proposed some of the beneficial methods for future research to make a robust product recommendation system.

Keywords: e-commerce, content-based filtering, collaborative-filtering, hybrid-filtering

1. Introduction

The technology for recommending the product to the users for E-Commerce becomes essential for improving the experiences of users with the rapid growth and popularity of E-Commerce. The recommendation of a product to individual users based on their preferences helps to increase the positive experiences for the users by providing appropriate suggestions. The aim of using E-Commerce product recommendation system is to provide relevant suggestions to the users based upon users' preferences by taking less time and effort of users. Another aim for using a recommendation system is to increase sales for generating more revenue. Product recommendation systems in E-Commerce also play an important role as a solution for information overload problems (Alamdari, et al., 2020).

Tewari & Mainwal (2019) proposed a recommendation system using collaborative filtering by using users' tags and rating

information of products available on E-Commerce websites to provide useful information to users and solve the information overload problems. The system proposed by Tewari & Mainwal (2019) adjusts the predicted ratings of recommended items using the standard deviation of items that predict the rating of products to the targeted user depending upon the profile of targeted users and other similar users.

Cao & Li (2007) developed a product-based personalized recommendation system depending upon product attributes to assist customers with product navigation. The customer has their own need in features for finding optimal products based on their preferences while navigating the products. Precision and recall were used to measure the effects of the proposed system. Similarly, F1 was also utilized to test the effects using a precision-recall combination.

Choi et al. (2012) also used metrics such as precision, recall, F1 to evaluate the accuracy of recommendations. Their goal was to integrate collaborative filtering and sequential pattern analysis to generate implicit ratings for improving recommendation quality. Four different experiments were conducted and concluded that implicit rating can easily replace formal rating in Collaborative filtering techniques. As well as there should be always a large set of data for generating an appropriate recommendation.

Product recommendation system based on knowledge was proposed by Prasad (2007) was related to the finding that prior users' purchase habits are important in recommending things to new users if the users followed previous part of the current patterns. CBRPR (Case-Based Reasoning Plan Recognition) and ACF (Automated Collaborative Filtering) were used to propose the knowledge-based recommendation system, which also addressed the challenges of organizing and utilizing information about items that a user purchases regularly. An experiment performed by Prasad (2007) noted that the outcomes of performance may vary a bit depending on interfaces difficulties such as the number of product presented and recommended at a time.

Wakil et al. (2020) developed an approach for assessing the effectiveness of recommendation systems. Some criteria for assessing the success of recommendation systems included history of customer, product categories, and product price criteria. Structural equations as modeling tools were utilized to test the method's validity to meet the researcher's objectives.

LU et al. (2015) proposed an enhanced content and collaborative filtering-based hybrid product recommendation algorithm to address the problems faced by traditional recommendation algorithms. The researchers solved the problems by using the proposed recommendation method. The researcher concluded that the hybrid recommendation methods can reduce the problem with single algorithms and enhance the efficiency and quality of recommendations with great user experiences.

This paper intended to focus on investigating several product recommendation methods and techniques that researchers have proposed. The Paper investigates the method and techniques adopted by other researchers for the recommendation of the product. Various approaches were proposed by different researchers. This paper also compares the methods for finding appropriate techniques for the recommendation of products.

2. Current Methods for Product Recommendation System

This section analyzed the current methods for a recommendation of products that use various approaches from several research papers. This section mainly focused on the use of content-based filtering, collaborative filtering, and hybrid filtering as a recommendation method. Similarly, the methodologies, results, and conclusions were analyzed based on these topics.

2.1 Content-Based Filtering

Weihong & Yi (2006) worked on an E-Commerce product recommendation system related to content filtering to explore users' unique interests to recommend products. A recommender list was generated by exploring users' unique features

depending on the value of the qualitative product information.

Fig.1: Weihong & Yi (2006) Architecture for Product Recommendation System based on Content-Based Filtering.

In an experiment performed by Weihong & Yi (2006), Data and recommender processing phases were separated in the system to extract the feature of the user's interest, its model, and similarity computation from the system. Data processing and recommender processing were two parts of the system where the system pre-processes the web-log history, access list and trade data first for identifying users' interests and forming a first recommender model. Then, the calculation of initial similarity between recommender models and recommender processing was performed. The product fits the consumers' interests, and the product's information served as a recommender access list for the users if the similarity degree is greater than or equal to the initial recommender model.

Weihong & Yi (2006) tested the system by using various information available on the web and server logs related to the product, such as products, product details, and their historical data. The experiment tested by Weihong & Yi (2006) explored that the users' individual interests were combined with a vector space model that could recommend products based on the information's qualitative worth. The aims, method, and experimental results on their

paper were good and would be useful for future research as well.

Xu et al. (2005) suggested an E-Commerce content-based recommendation approach that uses the properties of a product and the rating of products as classified data. The researcher came to conclude that the proposed system addressed the problems existing on traditional recommendation methods and increased the more targeted customers using content-based filtering.

Fig.2: Comparison of recommendation accuracy by Xu et al. (2005)

Researchers experimented and analyzed their proposed method with the cosine-based method and Corre-based method using sparse rating data. Xu et al. (2005) used MAE (Mean Absolute Error) as evaluated standard where the experiment showed that the methods proposed by Xu et al. (2005) increased the quality of recommendation than the cosine-based method and Corre-based method. The experiment performed by the researcher was valid and showed the good practice of science.

2.2 Collaborative Filtering

Jiang et al. (2018) applied a slope one method to the fusion of trustworthy data and similarity. of users for an efficient and effective recommendation of products. Researchers comprised slope one algorithm with the selection of reliable data, computation of similarities among users, and adding similarities to the weight factor of improved slope one algorithm.

Jiang et al. (2018) performed various experiments using Amazon's data. The aim of using the slope one algorithm with a collaborative filtering-based recommendation system was to solve the problems of recommendation system that didn't perform well and prove that recommendation system with slope one algorithm performed more accurately.

For Jiang et al. (2018) experiments, they used a part of the items rating dataset from Amazon. The generated dataset was further classified into a dataset for training and a dataset for the test. For the evaluation metrics, Jiang et al. (2018) used statistical accuracy metrics and evaluated with four different aspects. The fusion of trusted data comprising similarity and the algorithm based on trusted data utilizing MAE and RMSE (root mean square error), and the similarity of users under different dataset sizes were the different parts of the evaluation. Researchers performed all evaluations fairly.

The slope one algorithm was depend upon the merger of reliable data and similarity of user has enhanced forecast accuracy in tests of the recommendation system, which was presented fairly. Researchers did not bias the presented evaluations as researchers have mentioned that the lacking dramatic improvement on prediction because of the subjective behavior of people and fraudulent internet users.

Wang & Wang (2017) proposed an e-commerce recommendation system on the basis of an improved user-based collaborative filtering algorithm to improve the sparse data difficulties in collaborative filtering algorithm. Researchers combined the characteristics of user ratings with user

reviews and spark framework based on the latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA) model.

Fig.3: Wang & Wang (2017) System Framework Diagram

User information management module, user purchase and review records module, commodity information management module, and recommendation module were the four functional modules divided by the researcher for proposing recommendation system for E-Commerce.

Wang & Wang (2017) experimented on a recommendation system using the LDA model based on Spark to analyze user reviews, and generate the user preferences. Using the generated user preferences to calculate user preferences similarity, and combine user preferences similarity with the traditional user rating similarity to produce the final user similarity for generating recommended items. The experiment showed that the practical implementation of the proposed system has increased the standard of recommendation and effectively reduce the sparsity issue of collaborative filtering. The proposed aims by researchers were fulfilled and the experiment was valid.

2.3 Hybrid Filtering

Badriyah et al. (2017) developed an E-Commerce hybrid recommendation system implementing content-based filtering and collaborative filtering methods for computing product descriptions and user profiles' similarities. As a consequence of

their research, Badriyah et al. (2017) discovered that the recommendation is similar to the descriptions of goods and the preferences of user profiles, with an average precision and recall value. Researchers analyzed the recommendation made by the system using and computing the recall and precision values, as well as the necessary time for execution.

No.	a	b	(a+b)	c	(a+c)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)
1.	5	5	10	1	6	50	83.33
2.	6	4	10	2	8	60	75
3.	9	1	10	4	13	90	69.23
4.	7	3	10	5	12	70	58.33
Rata-rata						67.5	71.47

Fig.4: Badriyah et al. (2017) Result of Precision and Recall

However, the precision and recall value depend upon meant of relevant products and documents. The system developed by Badriyah et al. (2017) has a contribution on using the Text Mining TF-IDF (term frequency-inverse document frequency) techniques to construct automatically generated tags depending upon product descriptions. The generated tags are then combined with the profile of user to generate appropriate results to the user. Badriyah et al. (2017) followed a good science in their experiment and didn't introduce any bias at the time of presenting their results.

LU et al. (2015) proposed a hybrid filtering algorithm related to enhanced collaborative filtering of user context fuzzy clustering and content-based. The researcher chose precision and recall as evaluation metrics, which showed that the LU et al. (2015) also followed a good science in their experiment. LU et al. (2015) generated experimental results by contrasting their hybrid filtering recommendation algorithm with standard collaborative filtering and content-based

recommendation algorithms. Their experiments proved that considering clusters from users' information better reflects the intention of users for purchasing the product from an E-Commerce website. With the experimental results and their analysis researchers concluded that hybrid recommendation approaches decrease the problems of a single algorithm and are more suited for product recommendations in E-Commerce by playing a vital role in improving the recommendation quality and efficiency along with the enhancement of better users experiences.

Researchers included all the processes for developing algorithms, chosen metrics for evaluation, and the process of evaluation for generating the experimental results. All steps and results were written and presented clearly. So, that any researchers interested to research a similar topic can easily follow and conduct the research. All the aims, methods, or framework used, experimental results along experimental steps included on paper made a valid practice of good science.

3. Comparison of Methods

All the methods proposed by different researchers were appropriate and important for getting a quality recommendation of products on an E-Commerce Website. All the researchers have a unique measure and comparison, which made their proposed system even better compared to others. Various metrics were available for assessing the quality of the recommendation algorithms.

Wang & Wang (2017) and LU et al. (2015) both proposed an E-Commerce recommendation system on the basis of improved collaborative filtering algorithms and hybrid filtering algorithms for addressing the problems faced by traditional

recommendation algorithms such as data sparsity, cold start, and inefficiency. Their methods were able to meet the aims of their proposed system. However, the approaches proposed by LU et al. (2015) were able to address the problems faced by traditional recommendation algorithms as a hybrid recommendation on the basis of content and collaborative filtering able to avoid the problems faced using single algorithms for recommending the quality product to increase great users experiences. Approaches followed by LU et al. (2015) helped to increase the efficiency of recommendation as well.

The system proposed on content-based recommendation system for E-Commerce by Weihong & Yi (2006) and Xu et al. (2005) was focused on exploring user's interest with the vector space model and combination of the cluster to explore customer nearest neighbor, respectively. Both the proposed methods helped to increase the quality of the recommendation. Using precision, recall, and f-measures as evaluation metrics by Weihong & Yi (2006) made their research more appropriate for others researchers to carry out the research with the use of content-based filtering for recommendation systems for E-Commerce Store.

Jiang et al. (2018) presented a method of slope one algorithm that was depend upon the combination of trusted data and user similarity for collaborative filtering produced better results compared to Wang & Wang (2017) as Jiang et al. (2018) proposed system can be easily adopted on by other researchers for developing recommendation system with great user experiences from the recommended products.

Similarly, the process followed by Badriyah et al. (2017) can be implemented on

Weihong & Yi (2006) and Xu et al. (2005) proposed content-based filtering system for better improvements and fulfillment of quality recommendations. All the methods, experimental results, and evaluation metrics have their benefits to the proposed system.

4. Conclusion

This paper analyzed the current research on product recommendation systems where all the investigated papers were based on content-based, collaborative, and hybrid filtering methods. Recommendation systems used by E-Commerce using different approaches always aim to help customers to find the relevant product and help the owner to generate more sales. There were also various others approaches proposed by different researchers for creating the product recommendation system for E-Commerce. However, their limitations were that the proposed approaches were not scalable and usable for other systems and research. The proposed system based on collaborative and hybrid filtering approaches was appropriate to the E-Commerce for recommending the quality product and contribute to reducing information overload problem.

Some research methods analyzed in this paper, such as Jiang et al. (2018) and LU et al. (2015) allowed for the fusion of trusted data and users' similarities with the existing algorithms. Algorithms proposed by Jiang et al. (2018) can apply to various other recommendation systems for enhancing the quality recommendation of products.

Researchers can follow Jiang et al. (2018) for future research as all the performed experiments followed good science practices and results. Similarly, the proposed method by Badriyah et al. (2017) and Wang & Wang (2017) was appropriate to researchers for

producing robust product recommendation methods for an E-Commerce website.

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